

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TOLERANCE AS A SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CULTURE OF INTERETHNIC RELATIONS

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Abstract

The article deals with tolerance as socio-psychological phenomenon. The author states that the culture of interethnic relations in multicultural societies acquires special importance at all levels of their existence. Interethnic relations: perform important socio-psychological functions of socialization and social adaptation of the subjects of these societies; determine the nature, style, scenarios of individual and social life in these societies; determine the strategy and tactics of the development of these societies, their viability and competitiveness in the modern global world. The author of the article notes that the most common strategies of interethnic relations in multicultural societies are confrontational strategies (nationalism, discrimination, separation, isolation, genocide; marginalization strategies (assimilation, “dissolution”, leveling of interethnic differences); integration strategies (cooperation based on mutual understanding and partnership). Among the basic factors that determine the “quality” of the culture of interethnic relations in multicultural societies, perhaps the most important is tolerance. Based on the analysis of the scientific discourse, tolerance appears as a complex normative-valued social-psychological phenomenon, which: serves as a mental moral-valued regulator of social interaction at all levels of the functioning of the social system, which normalizes the awareness of social subjects of the value and uniqueness of their own and other ethnic cultures, attitude towards them (their norms, customs, traditions), desire and ability to effectively and conflict-free interact with them; is a technological tool for mediating and regulating the behavior of social subjects in the conditions of multicultural discourse and multicultural relations.

Introduction

Cultural, religious and ethnic pluralism of multicultural societies called for the development of tolerance as a condition for the successful civilizational development of these societies. Even today, interest in tolerance is determined not only by the demand of science, but primarily by the needs of social practice, which are especially relevant during social transformations in multi-ethnic societies (to which Ukrainian society also belongs).

The analysis of the concepts of tolerance presented in the professional literature makes it possible to talk about tolerance as a qualitative indicator of a multi-ethnic society, which performs a number of system-forming social functions (primarily, it is a development strategy and a tool for social harmony in multi-ethnic societies). And this gives grounds for determining tolerance, including as an important socio-psychological factor in the development of these societies, in particular, a factor in the development of the culture of interethnic relations in them.

Methodology

Concepts of tolerance established in scientific discourse

The term “tolerance” (or *tolerantia*, which is translated from Latin as tolerance, stability, endurance, indulgence to something, the ability to tolerate adverse influences (Dictionary of foreign words, 2000)) is one of those that do not have unambiguous Ukrainian equivalents (and this is quite important circumstance, because if a certain sociocultural marker is absent in the language, then it is unlikely to be represented in the mind), and therefore, it is advisable to analyze the evolution of this term and its meaning in other speech systems.

The foundations of the term “tolerance” were laid by the ancient philosophers Plato, Democritus, Aristotle, Herodotus and others, who considered tolerance as the main condition for spiritual freedom and personal development, which is impossible in conditions of violence and discrimination. According to this tradition, tolerance has long been interpreted within the framework of philosophy and religion.

Conceptions of tolerance as Christian tolerance are characteristic of the Middle Ages. Such tolerance relates to unconditional faith, cultivation of humility and obedience, submission to social requirements. Many philosophers, cultural scientists, researchers of religions and other spiritual spheres of human existence have devoted their works to the analysis of tolerance as a worldview phenomenon of divine origin. In particular, the ideas of tolerance were developed by philosophers, humanists and public figures of the Enlightenment and Reformation times (J. Locke, J. Milton, Voltaire, S. Mill, T. More, F. Rabelais, M. Luther). They actively debated in the treatises of J. Locke (“Essay on Tolerance”) and Voltaire (“Treatise on Religious Tolerance”). According to P. King, the classic idea of tolerance is best represented in the well-known aphorism of Voltaire, the author of the Treatise on Religious Tolerance, which reads: “I do not agree with what you say, but I will sacrifice my life defending your right to express your own opinion” (King, 1971). This humanistic idea is central to the philosophy of tolerance and serves as a basic indicator of a high culture of tolerance. At the same time, the Renaissance showed that any conviction - political, cultural, religious - can lead to intolerance, if there are no doubts about its truth and steadfastness.

The spirit of tolerance in the form of the ideas of humanism and nonviolence can be traced in the works

of Ukrainian philosophers and writers H. Skovoroda ("Not everything that is not understood is wrong", "When I want to be loved, I love myself first"), T. Shevchenko, L. Ukrainka, I. Franko, V. Stus, V. Symonenko, B. Grinchenko, V. Sukhomlynskyi, who consistently implemented universal and national values - humanism, mutual understanding, tolerance, happiness, goodness. In particular, T. Shevchenko considered goodness, love of freedom, non-violence, which can defeat evil and tyranny, to be the highest good. He highly valued moral qualities in people, instructions on the inadmissibility of cruelty and violence and their capacity for moral actions.

Nowadays, the term "tolerance" is one of the key terms in the sociology of culture (primarily in the discourse of the dialogue of cultures), as well as in political and social psychology (in the discourse of finding ways and means of consolidation, stable coexistence in conditions of multiculturalism). Thus, in the "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" (UNESCO, 1995), tolerance is interpreted as: a value and social norm of civil society, which appears as the right of all individuals of civil society to be equal; guarantee of stable harmony and constructive interaction between different social groups; respect for different world cultures, civilizations and peoples; willingness to understand and cooperate with people who differ in their appearance, language, beliefs and customs; skills of effective intercultural interaction, and it is also claimed that tolerance is "a correct understanding of the diversity of cultures in our world, our forms of self-expression, ways of expressing human individuality" (Declaration of Principles of Tolerance, 1995).

The theories and concepts of tolerance presented in modern psychological literature are quite diverse. For example, tolerance is defined as: approving behavior and refusal to impose one person's point of view on other people (N. Ashford); adoption of "rules of the game" (J. Sullivan, J. Marcus); respect for other people's views (O. Hryva); a certain quality of interaction (P. King) and relations (A. Horińska); reduced sensitivity to the object (O. Duhnitch); psychological stability; system of positive instructions; a set of individual qualities; system of personal and group values (I. Zhadan). In other authors' definitions or descriptions of tolerance, there are figurative juxtapositions of "one's own - another's", "we - they", "humans - non-human", "different - the same", etc.

Tolerance was actively studied by various psychological schools. Within the framework of the psychoanalytic approach, tolerance is interpreted in the context of the action of psychological defenses, strategies of coping behavior, human relations with the external environment, dialectics of self-identity and internal conflict (Z. Freud, E. Erikson, S. Folkman, K. Horney). Cognitive psychology provides material for understanding the mechanisms of tolerance/intolerance formation: identification, categorization, social attribution, stereotyping, reflection, and cognitive dissonance, among others (J. Turner, L. Festinger, F. Haider). In behaviorism, certain aspects of the manifestation of tolerance - intolerance are modeled, based on the satisfaction of social needs, the response to social fears, the adequate acceptance of the environment and oneself, the

formation of the foundations of aggressive behavior as a manifestation of intolerance (B. Skinner, J. Volpe, R. Lazarus, R. Beron, D. Richardson). Not the widest ideas of tolerance are presented in humanistic psychology, which reveals normative, value-orientational, directive, attitudinal, personal-meaningful aspects of tolerance (K. Rogers, A. Maslow, R. May). In the traditions of the humanistic approach, tolerance is a value and life position, the implementation of which in each specific situation has a certain meaning and requires the subject of tolerance to search for this meaning and make a responsible decision. According to T. Bilous, this is a manifestation of a person's conscious, active, responsible choice, this is his position (Bilous, 2004). According to the ideas of humanistic psychology, tolerance is the opposite of enmity, antipathy, and hatred. According to Yu. Habermas, this is a rejection of domination and violence, respect and recognition of the diversity and multidimensionality of human culture, a rejection of the search for the only correct point of view, recognition of the rights of others, acceptance of them as equals, one that claims understanding and compassion, readiness to accept representatives of other peoples and cultures as they are, and to interact with them on the basis of harmony and respect (Habermas, 2000). A lot of attention is paid to tolerance in cross-cultural and ethnic psychology, in particular, in studies of cultural and ethnic identity, ethno-cultural adaptation, tolerant worldview, culture of tolerance, etc. (J. Berry, D. Matsumoto, V. Harms and others).

Attempts to analyze the etymological roots of the term "tolerance" based on dictionaries of several languages were made by many domestic and Western scientists:

1) *tolero* (Latin) – bear, hold, endure, when it is connected with certain efforts, sufferings that a person must endure;

2) *tolerancia* (Spanish) – the ability to recognize other people's ideas and opinions, their difference from one's own, and to treat them tolerantly;

3) *tolerance* (French) - a relationship in the process of which a person recognizes that other people can and have the right to think or act differently from him;

4) *tolerance and toleration* (English) - from *tolerate* - to tolerate, to be tolerant, to admit, to allow - willingness to be patient (tolerant), to reconcile with the existence of something or someone, even if this "something" or "someone" becomes the cause of suffering, cause condemnation or disgust;

5) *kuan rong* (Chinese) – allow, accept, be merciful;

6) *tasamul'* (Arabic) – forgiveness, mercy, gentleness, patience, sensitive attitude towards others; patience - the ability to sustain physical or moral suffering, poverty, etc. without complaint; the ability to calmly endure boring, unpleasant, unwanted things for a long time.

As we can see, in almost all interpretations two connotations are explicitly or implicitly present – "patience" and "tolerance". These markers are the most correct Ukrainian equivalents of tolerance, including in the scientific discourse of social psychology. However, they should be differentiated.

In contrast to patience (from the Latin *patentia*, *patior* – endure, suffer), which etymologically has a passive meaning and means endurance of the body, pain, burden, suffering from calamities, etc.; common-sense tolerance towards those who have obvious differences from the members of their group; restraining negative emotions and not using violent behavior in relation to them, etc., the term “tolerance” is interpreted in a much broader, strategic sense, namely as a social, cultural and religious phenomenon that characterizes individual and collective consciousness and at the same time behavior, the sign of which - a positive attitude towards those whose thoughts and actions are alternative or not approved by the majority. The marker “tolerance” is used not so much in the everyday context as in the general human context, although it denotes a socio-psychological trait of a person, which manifests itself as a benevolent and respectful attitude towards others, regardless of their beliefs, behavior, and the ability to grasp the truth in all its aspects, realizing its limitations. So, tolerance is not weakness, but evidence of a conscious and mature personality, a mature social subject.

A. Maslow considers tolerance as one of the main principles that provides the key to understanding the essence of a person and ensuring mutual understanding between people as individuals, members of social groups, and members of society (Maslow, 1997). K. Rogers interprets tolerance as “absence of pride” and unconditional acceptance of another person, with his beliefs and problems based on empathic understanding and congruence. S. Schwartz believes that a person should not only listen to himself, accept himself, orient himself on his own experience, but also try to understand other people, consider their interests (Schwartz, 2004).

Tolerance does not mean forced restraint, the need not to go beyond the bounds of decent behavior in society, but a conscious acceptance of the value of the diversity of phenomena and situations presented by the surrounding world, recognition of the right and freedom of another person to be other, with his own views, beliefs, lifestyle, traditions, etc. This is the so-called “culture of doubt” that begins where and when the interests of individual people do not coincide, which creates a state of psychological discomfort that needs to be reconciled and settled.

Tolerance is one of the mechanisms of coexistence, bringing together people with different traditions and ideologies that make up a multicultural society. Thanks to the action of this mechanism, people unite both with those who share their beliefs, speak the same language, come from the same (or complementary) ethnic culture, and with those who differ from them, but defend their ideas with dignity, worldview, behavior patterns. Tolerance is what facilitates the transition from war to a culture of peace. In view of this, tolerance is a great achievement of mankind.

The opposition of tolerance is intolerance. Intolerance (and therefore, interethnic tension, dislike, mistrust, dissatisfaction and mutual claims between representatives of different ethnic groups) is a sign of a low culture of interethnic relations that arise from time to

time between individual and group subjects of these relations. The line between tolerance and intolerance is quite shaky: any belief - religious, political or cultural - can lead to intolerance and an intolerant attitude, if certain subjects of interethnic relations have no doubts about the truth and steadfastness of the ideas they believe in. But the most important thing is that tolerance gives hope for tolerance in return, and intolerance does not lead to anything other than intolerance.

Findings

Empirical manifestations of tolerance

Tolerance includes an empirical sign of individual and collective social subjects and such complex social systems as the state, society, culture, ethnic group, etc., and therefore this phenomenon has many types and forms of manifestation, which are defined as psychophysiological, sociocultural, socio-psychological (individual, group, ethnic) factors. Depending on the sphere of human existence - personal, interpersonal, social or societal - where tolerance takes place, it is about personal, religious, social, communicative, political, ethnic and inter-ethnic, pedagogical, gender and other types of it.

Currently, the research of personal tolerance, that is, tolerance as a personality trait, communicative tolerance; intercultural and interethnic tolerance is fulfilled. All these types and forms of tolerance characterize the general culture of society and the level of culture of interethnic relations inherent in it, and the degree of their development gives grounds for dividing world cultures into tolerant (open, democratic, with a high level of intercultural relations) and intolerant (authoritarian, closed, militant, with low level of intercultural relations).

Tolerance of society - as one of the basic principles of its functioning, a guarantee of its stability, openness and democracy and a guarantee of successful development - is largely determined by the personal tolerance of its members. Thus, O. Yaremchuk analyzes tolerance precisely as an integral quality of an individual, which determines his ability to interact with the environment and his own internal state in problematic situations, which guarantees his adaptation in society and protects him from confrontation with the surrounding world and himself (Yaremchuk, 2014). Tolerance as an integral personality quality means openness to communication; appreciation of the rights and freedoms of others and the desire to understand another point of view (without rejecting one's own position); the ability to compromise to reconcile cultural and ethnic differences. An important sign of tolerance, according to G. Ball, - the sense of value of one's own personality formed in an individual and with it - the value of another person's personality (Ball, 1997).

I. Bekh suggests considering two types of personal tolerance - sensual (related to the individual's resistance to environmental influences, weakened response to adverse factors due to reduced sensitivity) and dispositional (related to the individual's instructions, attitude towards himself, other people, to life in general). The mechanisms that activate this or that type of tolerance - as a way of a person's response to the social environment are different, but both operate at the cognitive, affective and behavioral levels (Bekh, 2006).

In turn, L.Honcharenko talks about “unmature” (based on the principles of trust and openness) and “mature” (based on the principles of social morality) personal tolerance and distinguishes three types of it (Honcharenko, 2009):

1) natural tolerance characteristic of preschool children, which ensures acceptance by the children of their parents even in the case of psychological or physical violence by the latter; signs of such tolerance are frankness, inquisitiveness, trustworthiness;

2) moral-willed tolerance, which is characteristic of adults and manifests itself as patience, guaranteed by self-control of emotions and behavior;

3) moral and ethical tolerance, which is based on acceptance of oneself and the environment and manifests itself as the ability to establish and maintain comfortable and non-conflicting relationships with oneself, other people, with the World, the perception of any “otherness” as an objective given, as a positive attitude, trust in others, associated with one's own self.

The view of tolerance as a moral quality of the individual is quite common. However, tolerance as a moral virtue has at least two drawbacks. The first is excessive conformity, which nullifies the importance of values and beliefs. The second is tolerance for violation of moral standards defined by society, indifference, which is manifested in a liberal attitude towards differences, even if these differences are reprehensible (when it comes to violations of universal human values).

As noted by M. Matios, manifestations of personal tolerance are very diverse. This is a critical dialogue and expansion of one's own experience; respect for another position and guidance on mutual understanding and mutual agreement of positions; a positive attitude towards another, whose opinion you do not share, but with whom you have to interact; condescension (including to the weakness of others, including with a certain amount of contempt for them); avoidance and indifference under the “mask of non-interference”, etc. (Matios, 2006). All this represents not so much a certain level of development of tolerance as its “quality”, the assessment of which requires qualitative criteria.

The opposition to personal tolerance is personal intolerance. The division of people into tolerant and intolerant is quite arbitrary. Each person can manifest this and that. However, the tendency to do one way or another can become a permanent personality trait. In his works T. Adorno, G. Allport and others believed that a tolerant person is characterized by:

1) awareness, (including one's own virtues and vices);

2) flexibility of thinking and resistance to frustration;

3) responsibility for one's own actions, decisions;

4) self-orientation;

5) a sense of security and protection, faith in one's own strength, reluctance to blame oneself and others for one's problems;

6) positive self-esteem, positive self-acceptance;

7) loyalty to the diversity of the world and points of view, the ability to act effectively in conditions of uncertainty;

8) social sensitivity, ability to empathize;

9) tolerance as the basis of understanding and successful interaction with anyone;

10) guidance on freedom and democracy both for oneself and for others (Adorno, 1993; Allport, 1960).

T. Adorno described one of the bright types of an intolerant personality - an authoritarian personality (dominant and inflexible, prone to aggression and control, prejudiced, cynical, non-empathetic, with impoverished emotions and feelings) and emphasized that a crisis social situation in a multi-ethnic society becomes favorable environment for the manifestation of these characteristics in relation to representatives of others, “not one's own” ethnic groups (Adorno, 1993).

Empirically, intolerance manifests itself differently:

1) as hidden intolerance, when the subject knows and understands the importance of the principles of tolerance and the danger of intolerant ideas and actions, but is guided by his own views, sympathies and prejudices and has a negative attitude towards representatives of certain socio-demographic and ethnic groups (however, this does not have a non-public nature and does not affect public attitudes and actions);

2) as verbal aggression: the subject considers it possible to publicly express intolerant ideas against representatives of certain socio-demographic groups or ethnic groups, but also considers it impossible to use violence on this ground, to suppress the rights of people based on the ethnic principle;

3) as aggressive intolerant behavior: the subject considers justified certain actions aimed at limiting activities or violence against the object of intolerance, openly demonstrating his aggressive position or explaining it in terms of social justice.

Typical examples of tolerance/intolerance at the level of interpersonal relationships are when parents put up with/do not put up with certain unacceptable behavior of their children; at the level of social relations - when one person tolerates/does not tolerate another's weakness; at the level of societal relations - when the monarch (state, society) tolerates/does not tolerate pluralism and dissent, recognizes/does not recognize the principles of respect for human rights, tolerates/does not tolerate national minorities or homosexuals, etc.

In contrast to personal tolerance, which is a natural trait of a person, laid down from birth, social and ethnic tolerance have an external character and are the result of upbringing, education and learning. According to the research of I. Bekh, who analyzed in detail tolerance in the communicative aspect, communicative tolerance as such, which manifests itself at the social level, including interethnic relations and, in fact, normalizes and regulates these relations, has two main forms:

1) valuable, which is based on value systems and value models of behavior, clear observance of the principles of tolerance, which, first, proclaim an unbiased attitude towards representatives of other socio-demographic and ethnic groups and the readiness to accept their opinions and behavior;

2) protectionist, in which the subject of tolerance - individual or collective (institute, organization, group) not only treats other subjects tolerantly and impartially,

but also helps those who suffer from intolerant relations, who are subjected to intolerant treatment from any side (Bekh, 2006).

Most often, communicative tolerance manifests itself in the sphere of social cognition, in the sphere of social relations, including exchange of thoughts and emotions; in the field of social behavior (Habermas, 2000). In all these areas, it is represented at the cognitive, affective and behavioral levels:

1) as a sense-making disposition of the worldview level, which is based on the awareness of the peculiarities of one's culture, one's ethnicity and the cultures of other peoples and ethnicities (or at least on the conscious assumption that these peculiarities exist) and is manifested in a critical assessment of others and, together with this, in a desire to interact with it and enrich one's own experience;

2) as a positive attitude towards representatives of other ethnic groups, tolerant perception of their ethnocultural differences;

3) as socially acceptable styles of interaction, relations, and behavior for everyone.

The view of tolerance as a worldview instruction and a value-oriented disposition of the subject seems quite promising. Tolerance as a generalized disposition of an individual, fixed by his social experience, is manifested in the readiness to behave in a certain way and to perceive and evaluate himself and other subjects from his environment. This disposition is realized in social, ethnic, political and other relations as the ability to show tolerance, perceive without aggression and respond positively to the thoughts, actions, behavior, lifestyle, customs, feelings, ideas, beliefs of other people (social groups), even if they are significantly do not match their own. According to P. King, tolerance is a readiness not only to contact, dialogue, interact with the bearers of other views, but also to provide them with help if they need it (King, 1971).

Therefore, tolerance is not a passive contemplation, but a conscious and active attitude (a social position that is formed based on recognition of the basic universal rights and freedoms of another person and clearly prescribes the limits of tolerance) and appropriate behavior. Thus, a person should not be tolerant of violation of norms and values of universal morality, violation of another person's rights. Regarding the acceptable limits of tolerance, M. Walzer claims that the only thing to which tolerance should be unequivocally intolerant is intolerance. M. Walzer called it the "paradox of tolerance" (Walzer, 2000). In this sense, tolerance appears as an effective regulator of social behavior.

The behavioral aspect of tolerance is the most accessible for empirical observation. After all, in this sphere, tolerance is not only declared, but also actually demonstrated as specific emotions, empathy, positive attitude and specific – tolerant or intolerant – actions and behavioral acts:

1) personal, intragroup contacts, cooperation, dialogues (which guarantee comfortable and productive communication, exchange of information, enrichment of experience, etc.);

2) manifestations of mutual sympathy, empathy, respect (which guarantees the emotional exchange of

communication subjects and maintenance of their emotional comfort);

3) interaction aimed at achieving common mutually beneficial goals (which guarantees comfortable and productive interaction and cooperation and obtaining the desired joint result).

In turn, it should be noted that, according to many researchers, productive interaction (cooperation) based on tolerance is possible in conditions of active communicative exchange, when participants are aware of its goals, wish to obtain a significant result and understand their contribution to joint action. Such interaction is characterized by a number of features (and is possible under a number of conditions). These are:

1) activity in establishing contacts;

2) the desire to negotiate and the ability to compromise;

3) mutual trust;

4) tolerance for different views, opinions and positions;

5) attention and respect for each other;

6) emotional stability and positive emotional exchange;

7) help to everyone who needs it (Bilous, 2004).

All this is important information for diagnosing tolerance and its development in conditions of special educational and formative influences.

Personal and communicative (social) tolerance is most clearly manifested in inter-national and inter-ethnic relations. Ethnic and interethnic tolerance (or, on the contrary, intolerance) is primarily tolerance of other cultures and their values, acceptance of other logics of existence, other ways of perceiving the world, and at the empirical level, it is always a problem of the attitude of one ethnic group to another. These phenomena stand among others, which also embody the principles of universal morality and universal rules of conduct, manifested in honor and respect for all peoples of the world; awareness of the unity and common interrelationship of different ethnic cultures; non-acceptance of any forms of violence in relations between their representatives; solving inter-ethnic and problems based on the balance of interests. So, interethnic tolerance is, on the one hand, a system of psychological instructions, feelings, a certain set of knowledge and social and legal norms (expressed through law or traditions), as well as worldview and behavioral orientations, which assume a tolerant or acceptable attitude of representatives of any nationality (in particular, at the personal level) to others (their language, culture, customs, norms of behavior, etc.). On the other hand, it is the absence of a negative response to representatives of other ethnic cultures, the absence of a negative attitude towards another ethnic culture, as well as a positive image of another ethnic culture while maintaining a positive perception of one's own. According to S. Schwartz, the main sign of interethnic tolerance is formed positive images of one's own and "alien" ethnicities, and this is what makes it an effective factor of understanding and inter-ethnic integration (Schwartz, 2004).

Ukrainian researcher G.S. Kozuhar proposes to analyze manifestations of tolerance on three levels, which represent the logic of the formation of tolerance as a socio-psychological phenomenon and its content at

each of the levels of its development - dispositional, reflexive and behavioral (Kozhukhar, 2016).

The first level is informational and dispositional, i.e. the level of information and value-meaning systems and basic instructions of the individual for open relations with the world and its main subjects. The second level is reflective, or the level of social perception and instructions regarding the external situation (activation of instructions, stereotypes, and other cognitions that mediate reflective processes). The third level is behavioral, or the level of responding to the situation in the "here and now" mode based on the principles of tolerance/intolerance (Kozhukhar, 2016).

One of the manifestations of tolerance at the macro level of the social system is state paternalism, under which the state - as a secular institution - shows tolerance towards religious and other groups (if they do not question its authority), "tolerates" the existence of ethnic minorities (number and rights of which do not reach permissible limits and, therefore, are regulated by the state), demonstrates the same attitude towards representatives of different faiths, different moral norms, atheists, etc. etc., guided by the idea of the common good. Thanks to this, the inclusion of citizens in society and its unity are more possible than in the case of coercion.

According to E. Erickson, tolerance lies on the border between ethnic identity (constant contact with representatives of a certain nationality, positive attitude and complete acceptance of them) and ethnic intolerance (negative attitude, reluctance to maintain any contact with representatives of a certain nationality, complete rejection). E. Erickson developed a scale of social distance (and as an option - interethnic tolerance), which is based on five levels of closeness of social subjects:

- 1) "perception of other people as personal friends" (high positive level);
- 2) "perception of others as neighbors living on my street" (medium positive level);
- 3) "perception of others as work colleagues who have the same profession" (normal level);
- 4) "perception of others as citizens of my country or as tourists visiting my country" (medium negative level);
- 5) "I would not prefer to see these people in my country, I would expel them from the country" (high negative level) (Erickson, 1996).

This scale takes into account the already mentioned dimensions of tolerance: 1) cognitive-value (formed system of values, guidelines, motivation regarding interaction, cooperation, tolerant behavior); 2) affective (emotions, feelings, attitude); 3) interactive, behavioral (suggestions and reactions to social interaction with participants in intercultural communication, leading models of interaction and behavior, etc.).

In the just-defined theoretical and empirical dimensions (cognitive-value, emotional-attitudinal and behavioral), we propose to analyze tolerance as a system-forming feature and a factor in the development of the culture of interethnic relations, which is empirically manifested on the individual (personal and social, including interpersonal, intra- and intergroup) and supra-individual, societal levels of its functioning. We put the

idea of such a three-level structure of tolerance as the basis of a theoretical (and further empirical) model of our research.

Socio-psychological collisions of tolerance

One of the collisions is obvious inconsistencies between:

1) systems of knowledge and ideas about tolerance, which exist in the form of certain more or less systemic mental constructs in individual and mass consciousness and are manifested mainly at the societal or macro level of the functioning of social systems (conditionally let's call it declared tolerance);

2) informational, behavioral, emotional actions and interactions (both their content and their density), which are exchanged among the participants of social communication at the social, i.e., intra- and intergroup levels (let's tentatively call it demonstrated or feigned tolerance);

3) personal tolerance, which is primarily manifested at the micro-level of the functioning of social systems, in interpersonal contacts and relationships, which is based on deep tolerance beliefs, a high level of personal culture and the culture of tolerance of individual and group bearers (let's tentatively call it true tolerance). These three levels of tolerance can harmoniously coincide and complement each other, or they can be in a state of inconsistency or conflict.

It would be quite logical to assert (and this is what tolerance researchers most often emphasize) that tolerant behavior is possible only on the basis of tolerant consciousness, in particular with the presence and actualization of the value-meaning resource of the subjects of social interaction, in the process of which they appear from time to time faced with a choice: to be tolerant, maintain dialogue and interact, even if at the same time one has to overcome a state of cognitive dissonance and psychological discomfort, or, on the contrary, to be intolerant. After all, if tolerance is a valuable orientation of the individual, then, according to G.S. Kozhuhar, on one pole there is acceptance and support, and on the other - disagreement (cognitive level of response) and negative emotions (affective level of response) (Kozhuhar, 2016).

Tolerant ideas, which in themselves are certainly worthy of respect, firstly, are not shared by everyone and from time to time are exposed to sharp criticism, and secondly, do not always serve as a guide to action in real everyday life. And for this there are serious deep-rooted reasons connected with the socio-cultural features of society, that is, with the features of its philo- and sociogenesis (which is passed on from generation to generation to members of society and has mostly a worldview character) and with its socio-psychological features, or ontogenetic stories possible in this society (what is acquired and strengthened in the course of the individual life of members of society in the conditions created by it, regulations, controls and sanctions and is mainly of a practical, behavioral nature).

One of the most profound basic prerequisites for tolerance, as O.V. Petrunko, writes is:

- 1) recognition of the existence of "otherness" (everything different from what you are, not identical to you) as such, which is not an opposition, but an equal alternative to "identity";

- 2) unbiased attitude towards "otherness";
- 3) willingness to interact with it (Petrunko, 2018).

This extremely important property of an individual, according to E. Erikson, is inherited from birth as a part of unconscious collective knowledge, as an instruction to trust the world ("basic trust in the world") (Erickson, 1996). The opposition to this is "basic mistrust of the world", of any "otherness", which necessarily involves the division of subjects of social interaction into "own" and "others", which limits interaction, while the alternative is that quantitatively and qualitatively enriches it.

The picture of a bipolar world laid down in early childhood is restored and established every time during the entire further life of a person. First, through folk tales, proverbs and various works for children, where there is always Good and Evil, which necessarily compete. Then - in educational systems based on polar worldview models. Subsequently - in the sphere of influence of mass media and various modern media. Nowadays, there is no doubt that in media societies the authority and influence of traditional institutions of socialization, their priority in shaping the worldview of children and youth is weakened to the extent that this role is taken over by means of media communication. Media is not only an extremely effective substitute for traditional socialization and educational systems, but also a tool for influencing the outlook and psychological well-being of subjects of social interaction with the help of manipulative technologies, including and through the creation of new myths and images of internal and external enemies.

A world based on mutual mistrust, closedness to dialogue and any "otherness" in general is a world characterized by a low level of general culture, including culture of tolerance, where the basic worldview and behavior formula is "those who are not with us are against us" This is partly why a common enemy, whether internal or external, is an extremely effective factor in the organization of a bipolar world. Both the real enemy and his image, artificially constructed in people's minds, are capable of reorienting the thoughts, feelings, and actions of large numbers of people. The image of a common enemy and the natural fear of loss of identity or physical destruction activate, on the one hand, patriotic feelings, the value of traditions and state symbols, the need to preserve (at any cost!) the integrity of the country, etc., and on the other hand, the motivation of self-preservation and protection, which supplants the motivation for tolerance and development. All this permeates individual and social life at all levels, makes people suggestive, predictable and controlled, which is successfully used by "consciousness manipulators". The acquired (consolidated during the personal ontogenetic history of life) experience of personal and social tolerance/intolerance manifests itself in the corresponding style of tolerant/intolerant behavior.

Another paradox is that in situations of social communication, which a priori, by definition, requires the activation of tolerance guidelines and skills of tolerant behavior, two categories of cognitions are usually involuntarily actualized:

- 1) associated with memories of previous, and mostly negative, experiences of similar situations;

- 2) associated with uncomfortable expectations, anxiety, fears due to this situation.

So, these are potentially stressful situations. They are automatically classified as threatening, which also automatically triggers a stress reaction and increases the level of psycho-emotional and physiological tension. Thus, the question arises about the need for their correct recognition and interpretation.

Conclusions

In a multicultural society, the quality of interethnic relations acquires special importance, the main system-forming indicator of which is the culture of interethnic relations. The culture of interethnic relations is a system-forming moral and value category, which means awareness by its bearers of the peculiarities and value of their own and other cultures, respect and a positive, tolerant attitude towards their own and other cultures (their norms, religion, customs, traditions), the desire and ability to effectively interact with them without conflict.

The culture of interethnic relations manifests itself differently at all levels of the functioning of social systems - individual and supra-individual (or on micro-, meso-, and macro-levels), and its quality is determined by:

- 1) the awareness of the subjects of interethnic communication about each other's peculiarities (traditions, habits, peculiarities of behavior, psychological features, etc.), as well as ethnic stereotypes, guidelines, values, etc. formed in them (social or macro factors);

- 2) the quality of communication between them, including high-quality exchange of information, including speech competence, quality interactions, exchange of emotions, feelings, attitudes, etc. (social-psychological, or meso-factors);

- 3) the quality of personal communication, which involves knowledge of the peculiarities of other cultures, a trusting attitude towards them, readiness to interact with and maintain interpersonal and social relations with them (individual-psychological factors).

The main feature of quality interethnic relations is personal and interethnic tolerance, which manifests itself at all levels of functioning of social systems of different levels of organization as a multidimensional and multifunctional disposition of social subjects ("tolerant consciousness") and their tolerant behavior, which together guarantee an adequate response of different ethnic groups and their representatives against each other and is a tool for achieving understanding, reducing inter-ethnic tension, and settling inter-ethnic conflicts. Consequently, tolerance appears as a multifunctional phenomenon (a way of thinking, a guideline, a common human value, a norm of social life, a principle and a certain "emotional pattern" of human relations, a style of behavior, etc.), which performs a number of strategic and regulatory functions for the implementation of a "dialogue" of cultures.

Empirical indicators of tolerance are divided into three groups:

- 1) cognitive and axiological: awareness of the history, religion and culture of one's own and other ethnic groups; awareness of gender, social, psychological characteristics of representatives of these ethnic groups; understanding of modern interethnic processes

and phenomena, as well as guidelines, values and ethnic stereotypes in the field of cultural and ethnic traditions;

2) emotional and attitudinal: openness to contacts and interaction and a positive attitude towards representatives and values of one's own and other ethnic groups);

3) instrumental-behavioral (communicative skills; knowledge of other languages; skills of tolerant thinking and behavior; skills of self-control and control of aggression, as well as personal qualities of the tolerance spectrum (respect and tolerance for "otherness", social flexibility, empathy, social activity, emotional stability etc.) Thus, we can talk about three dimensions of tolerance - cognitive-axiological, emotional-attitudinal and instrumental-behavioral.

References:

1. Adorno T. Types and syndromes // *Socis.*, 1993. No. 3. P. 75-86.
2. Allport G. W. *Personality and social encounter: Selected essays.* Boston: Beacon Press, 1960. 188 p.
3. Ball G. On the relationship between principledness and tolerance // *Pedagogy of tolerance*, 1997. No. 1-2. P. 110-111.
4. Bekh I.D. *Personality education: ascent to spirituality.* K.: Lybid, 2006. 272 p.
5. Bilous, T. *Education of tolerance in students of higher pedagogical educational institutions in the process of learning a foreign language: dissertation. ... candidate of ped. sciences: 13.00.07.* Rivne, 2004. 227 p.
6. Declaration of Principles of Tolerance [Electronic resource]. 1995. URL: <http://www.tolerance.ru/declar.html>.
7. *Dictionary of foreign words / Compilation.* S.M. Morozov, L.M. Shkaraputa. Kyiv: Naukova dumka, 2000. 662 p.
8. Erikson E. The concept of ego identity // *Journal of American Psychoanalytic Association.* 1996. № 4. P.56-121.
9. Habermas, Yu. *Structural transformations in the field of openness: a study of the civil society category: Translated from German.* Lviv: Litopys, 2000. 320 p.
10. Honcharenko L. A. *Multicultural education of the teacher: theory and practice.* Kherson: RIPO, 2009. 136 p.
11. King, P. *The problem of tolerance: Government and opposition.* The London school of economics and political science / P. King. L.: Univ. of London, 1971. P. 172-207.
12. Kozhukhar G.S. *The problem of tolerance in interpersonal communication // Questions of Psychology*, 2016. No. 2. P. 3-12.
13. Maslow, A. *The Far Limits of the Human Psyche.* St. Petersburg: Eurasia, 1997. 430 p.
14. Matios M.V. *Nation. Revelation.* Lviv: LA "PYRAMIDA", 2006. 204 p.
15. Petrunko O.V. *Inherited and acquired experience of intolerance // Collection of scientific articles of Kyiv International University and the Institute of Social and Political Psychology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. Series "Psychological sciences: problems and achievements". Issue 6.* K.: KyMU, 2018. P. 145-155.
16. Schwartz, S. *Mapping and interpreting cultural differences around the world // Comparing cultures, dimensions of culture in a comparative perspective: H.Vinken, J.Soeters, & P. Ester (Eds.).* Leiden, The Netherlands, 2004. P. 43-73.
17. Walzer M. *On Tolerance; trans. from English by I. Mürnberg.* Idea-Press, House of Intellectual Books, 2000. 160 p.
18. Yaremchuk O. V. *Ethnocultural myth-making of Ukrainians // Ethnopsychological dimension of Ukraine: semiosis, myth-making, identity.* K.: LLC NVP "Interservice", 2014. P. 45-100.

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